

MIGNEX Survey Dataset (open-access variant)

This metadata sheet describes the *open-access variant* of the MIGNEX Survey Dataset, which has been anonymized to prevent identification of individuals. There is a corresponding, restricted-access variant of the dataset with more fine-grained data for use by the project team.

Data type	Survey data
Unit of analysis	Individuals
Geographical coverage	25 research areas across 10 countries in Africa, the Middle East and Asia (Cabo Verde, Guinea, Ghana, Nigeria, Ethiopia, Somalia, Tunisia, Turkey, Afghanistan, and Pakistan)
Timespan	Data collected between November 2020 and February 2022
Sample size	N = 12,973 (Based on a target sample of 500 individuals in each research area) ¹
Population	General population aged 18–39
Data origin	Computer-Assisted Personal Interviews (CAPI) using tablets
Thematic coverage	Individual demographic and socio-economic information, household-level demographic and socio-economic information; household's migration experiences and connections to migrants; migration experiences, aspirations, and preparations; attitudes towards migration, perceptions of local and national development.
Data file(s)	mignex-survey-dataset-open-access-variant-v1.dta (released 1 September 2024)
Dataset citation	Please cite as displayed on the Zenodo page for this record.
Detailed documentation	<p>Hagen-Zanker J., Hennessey G., Carling J. and Memon R. (2023) <i>Survey data collection</i>, MIGNEX Handbook Chapter 7 (v2). Oslo: Peace Research Institute Oslo. Available at www.mignex.org/d031.</p> <p>Hagen-Zanker, J., Carling, J., Caso, N., Hennessey, G., and Rubio, M. (2023) <i>Documentation of survey data</i>, MIGNEX Handbook Chapter 10 (v3). Oslo: Peace Research Institute Oslo. Available at https://www.mignex.org/d032. See section 10.13 of this document for details on how variables have been modified for the sake of anonymization.</p> <p>See also zenodo.org/communities/mignex for additional data and documentation and mignex.org for project information and publications.</p>
Dataset managers	Jessica Hagen-Zanker (ODI) and Jørgen Carling (PRIO)

¹ The dataset includes an additional 199 cases in a 26th research area where data collection was interrupted for security reasons.